

Efficient Digital Voice and Chat Communications through Generative AI at the Tactical Edge

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Abstract

In this paper, we aim to improve chat and audio services in Disconnected, Intermittent and Limited (DIL) environments. Putting emphasis on the tactical edge and inspired by the NATO Federated Mission Networking (FMN) initiative, we apply artificial intelligence (AI) to improve these collaboration services.

The paper discusses the design and architecture of such next-generation collaboration services, where AI empowers the application to provide text-to-speech and speech-to-text capabilities, connected via an efficient message distribution mechanism. To achieve a realistic and immersive communication experience, we introduce generative AI on the receiver side to reconstruct audio messages with characteristics similar to the original speaker. Our experimental results show that this approach significantly reduces the strain on tactical networks by lowering data rate requirements—achieving up to 93.7% reduction in transmitted media data compared to traditional voice codecs, and 72% reduction when including signaling overhead—while maintaining low end-to-end latency, typically under two seconds.

This work has been conducted as part of the NATO research task group IST-201.

1 INTRODUCTION

Federated Mission Networking (FMN) is an initiative aiming to allow NATO nations to develop and agree on their federation requirements [1]. In this respect, processes, procedures, and technical solutions must be standardized. Ultimately, this NATO initiative should lead to unsurpassed command and control (C2) capabilities in coalition missions in any operating environment. The vision is called "o-Day Interoperable Forces", which means that the participants in operations should be able to instantiate mission networks as needed. These networks should support mission requirements, including multiple levels of classification as needed, facilitating interoperable information sharing at strategic and tactical levels.

The federation aspect must be built on mutual trust so that participants may form a single collaborative entity. However, within this entity, participating NATO Nations still retain autonomy of their national systems. FMN commits them to a common process and interoperability guidelines through common procedures and standardized interfaces. This means that the aspect of "networking" includes both the human dimension (interactions between people and the need for a common vocabulary and understanding) and the technological dimension (Information Communication Technology (ICT) systems that can exchange data and provide a common operational picture (COP)).

The connected forces originating from FMN will have several benefits: interoperability, faster setup, rapid deployment, better information sharing, and also the prospect of improved collective efficiency and cost

savings through resource pooling. The FMN initiative is therefore central to NATO and is also a main motivating factor in the work of the IST-201 research task group.

The IST-201 is a research group dedicated to advancing collaboration services through the integration of AI-driven innovations. Its primary focus includes improving audio and chat services to deliver better communication, collaboration, and user experience. The group leverages on artificial intelligence technologies (including generative AI (GenAI)) to optimize voice recognition, natural language processing, audio generation, and real-time interactions, making these services more efficient, intelligent and accessible, even at the tactical edge.

The research scope of IST-201 in the context of tactical communications focuses on developing solutions for narrowband radios with limited data rates, operating in constrained environments with irregular connectivity. This is particularly crucial in military settings where soldiers need reliable voice communication in challenging conditions. The group aims to enhance communication systems that can operate effectively despite bandwidth limitations and sporadic connectivity, ensuring that voice communications remain clear and continuous in tactical environments.

Realized as part of IST-201 activities, this paper presents an efficient approach for exchanging audio messages between soldiers, particularly in environments with limited connectivity. It enables soldiers to maintain crucial contact and share information efficiently despite bandwidth and connectivity constraints. It is structured as follows: Section 2 presents the background for the topic, mentioning prior work conducted

to efficiently exchange data in tactical environments, including approaches to enable audio communications. Section 3 describes the proposed implementation to further improve audio communications, by generating messages from audio and by applying GenAI techniques for audio reconstruction of received messages, mimicking the sender modulated voice. Section 4 describes results obtained from experiments conducted over an emulated tactical network. The discussion in section 5 frames our findings in context of the future of C2. The paper is concluded in section 6.

2 BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

The tactical edge refers to the operational environment at the forefront of military operations, where soldiers, vehicles, and equipment engage directly with adversaries. It is characterized by dynamic, often unpredictable conditions, including challenging terrain, limited resources, and sporadic or unreliable communication networks, i.e., Disconnected, Intermittent and Limited (DIL) environments. At the tactical edge, connectivity can be constrained due to factors like narrowband radio systems, interference, distance, and environmental obstacles, which create challenges for communication, data sharing, and decision-making.

In this context, it is crucial to achieve real-time situational awareness and effective command and control at the tactical edge where soldiers need reliable, low-latency communication tools to exchange vital information, such as voice, audio, or data, despite the limitations imposed by the environment. Enhancing communication technologies at the tactical edge is key to ensure that operations remain effective and responsive, even when operating in isolated or hostile settings.

Work conducted by [2] proposed a concept for soldier systems involving IoT, and smart devices enabling digital services in a networked environment. The system brought automated functions and reporting mechanisms, including location, body movement and posture, environmental data, health vitals and status and multimedia capabilities (for ISR and communications). It was demonstrated the capability to exchange non-streaming IoT data, like location, using an efficient message-broker mechanism.

As part of group IST-150 [3], [4], that specifically studied services profiling for hybrid tactical networks including DIL networks, experimented different protocols over emulated tactical networks. For message-oriented middleware, the group recommended the use of the MQTT¹ open standard over alternatives like WS-Notification. While MQTT offers a lightweight implementation, it yields two major disadvantages:

reliance on a centralized server represents a single-point of failure; and operating over TCP represents a performance bottleneck.

To address the above limitations, subsequent experiments in [5] tested different MQTT non-standard configurations, including a decentralized mesh broker (using VerneMQ²) and MQTT/UDP³ reaching the following findings:

- MQTT/UDP exhibited superior performance in low-bandwidth networks, but had a higher packet losses compared to the standard TCP-based flavors of MQTT;
- the clustering mechanism in VerneMQ eliminated the single-point-of-failure vulnerability but introduced overheads and exhibited worse performance than using standard MQTT.

MQTT (and especially the modified MQTT/UDP) is a promising protocol for message-based data exchange in tactical networks. While communications services typically rely on data streaming protocols, our work shows the application of MQTT (as a message distribution mechanism) enabling digital voice communications in DIL environments.

2.1 DIGITAL COMMUNICATION SERVICES AT THE TACTICAL EDGE

Deployed forces at the tactical edge need collaboration services, including communication capabilities for team members. Communication may occur in various forms, including video, audio and chat, ideally in digital format. However, tactical networks' DIL nature limit the application of digital rich communications especially due to bandwidth and latency constraints. This work investigates AI-enabled mechanisms to realise efficient audio communication at the tactical edge.

Digital audio communication typically involves transmitting continuous data streams from source to destination. The required bandwidth depends on the selection of the audio codec. Earlier work by the IST-201 group [6] analysed several codecs fit for slow networks, including MELP (Mixed-Excitation Linear Predictive, standardized as STANAG 4591, specifically the enhanced MELPe and MELP-WB codecs)⁴ and Lyra⁵ requiring bitrates between 2.4 and 3.2 kbps, which is deemed to be appropriate for most tactical networks.

In [7], a disruptive approach to reduce the strain on the network was suggested by resorting to AI-enabled services (i.e., speech-to-text (STT)) delivering real-time transcription of voice messages, making it easier to exchange information even when network

¹Available at <https://mqtt.org/>

²Available at <https://vernemq.com/>

³Available at <https://mqtt-udp.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁴See <https://melp.org/>

⁵Available at <https://github.com/google/lyra>

reliability is poor. The generated text message was then transmitted using a MQTT message-broker. At the receiver side, text-to-speech (TTS) modulation is used to optimize audio output, ensuring clearer and more intelligible voice communication. This optimization is especially beneficial in noisy settings.

The approach aimed to improve the overall quality and reliability of communication, helping soldiers maintain effective and efficient exchanges of critical information in demanding environments. It was demonstrated to significantly reduce the original audio size⁶

The STT achieved a high accuracy, however issues and risks, associated with wrong translations, should be expected when using less common words or languages. Moreover, one major disadvantage with the implemented approach consisted in having the TTS audio reconstruction not mimicking the speaker modulation, making impossible to associate the audio with the identity of the speaker.

3 ARCHITECTURE AND IMPLEMENTATION

The approach proposed to achieve efficient audio communications builds upon the architecture introduced in [7], but extends it significantly to support real-time processing and improve system modularity. While [7] primarily focused on a functional pipeline using STT, TTS, and MQTT messaging, our current work refactors the system into independent, containerized components with RESTful APIs. This modular design enables real-time sentence detection and processing during an active call, allowing the system to handle live audio streams rather than relying on file-based processing. Figure 1 illustrates the updated architecture and the deployment setup used in our demonstrator.

There are two core elements in our approach:

The first is Linphone, an open-source Voice over IP (VoIP) software⁷. Linphone supports the SIP (Session Initiation Protocol) standard, which makes it compatible with a wide range of VoIP systems and providers. Linphone is easily extensible by adding "filters" and defining custom processing flows. Our work involves multiple steps and transformations integrating four key technologies: transcription (i.e., STT), speech generation (i.e., TTS), message distribution mechanism, and VoIP.

The second component is the message distribution middleware component connecting message senders (i.e., publisher) and receivers (i.e., subscribers) clients. Based on our previous work, we opted for a MQTT-

⁶A sample of 10 seconds uncompressed audio message with 23 spoken words was used. The converted text message in UTF-8 takes about 98 bytes. If using the Lyra codec, which requires 8 kbps for transmitting, the audio message size would be about 10 kB.

⁷Available at <https://www.linphone.org>

compliant message broker that operates following the publish-subscribe model and is fit for tactical networks. As per recommendations of IST-150, we use quality of service (QoS) 1, since it guarantees message delivery. The MQTT client sender-side involves using Linphone to capture audio and transcribing it into text. The text message is then published to the MQTT server using a specific topic. The MQTT client server-side receives the message via MQTT that can be listened using Linphone after applying TTS. Since we operate over limited tactical networks, we use MQTT/UDP⁸, a brokerless MQTT variation that replaces the use of TCP with UDP for improved performance in DIL networks.

The architecture was designed for a clean separation of concerns by outsourcing the functionalities of STT, TTS, and MQTT messaging into separate components (Docker containers) with dedicated RESTful interfaces. This modular design allows components to be easily replaced or extended—such as adding support for new transcription languages—without affecting the overall system.

We resorted to open source software to establish a baseline which facilitates real-time audio dissemination in distributed environments comprising 3 virtual machines (VM).

The communication between the two Linphone VMs used in the demonstrator is emulated by a Swiss Radio Model in the Extendable Mobile Ad-hoc Network Emulator (EMANE), which models the characteristics of military radios, specifically, TDMA-based VHF and UHF based radios [8]. The model contains a narrowband waveform (VHF) and a wideband waveform (UHF) with configurable data rates.

The main architectural components are introduced next.

3.1 LINPHONE EXTENDED WITH SPEECH/TEXT CODEC FILTER

Linphone supports the integration of "filters", being building blocks used to process multimedia streams that can handle tasks such as encoding, decoding, mixing, and applying effects (e.g., noise reduction). Each filter is a standalone component performing a specific functionality. There are dedicated filters for sending and receiving streams over the network. They can be dynamically configured and connected based on the type of media and network conditions.

Filters can be connected into a graph to form a processing pipeline for audio or video. The pipeline manages the flow of data from input (e.g., microphone or camera) to output (e.g., speaker or file).

We have implemented a speech/text codec filter in

⁸Available at: https://github.com/dzavalishin/mqtt_udp

Figure 1: Speech-to-Text and Text-to-Speech Architecture. Three VMs are depicted: the left one (i.e., Linphone VM (1)) refers to the sender; the right one (i.e., Linphone VM (2)) refers to the receiver; the center one emulates a tactical radio network.

Linphone. The filter receives audio input from the microphone or a file (in WAV format) and forwards it to the STT component (see Subsection 3.2), receiving back the transcribed message in text format. Conversely, when receiving a text message, the filter forwards it to the TTS component (see Subsection 3.3), receiving back the generated message in audio format.

3.2 STT COMPONENT

In previous work as part of IST-201 activities we have investigated an approach to improve collaboration services through the use of AI-models that specialize in transcribing speech to text [7]. To showcase its potential, we developed a service that transcribed the voice of a user to text. The text is then transmitted across a network to a receiving user, where the service transcribes the text back to voice or use the text as a message in a chat-application.

For making STT work in a realtime environment with Linphone, some challenges had to be solved. To improve the accuracy of STT transcription, we segment incoming audio into complete sentences prior to processing. Sentence-level transcription yields higher semantic coherence and improved recognition performance, as automatic speech recognition (ASR) models typically perform better on longer, context-rich utterances compared to isolated fragments. We implemented silence-based segmentation using the pydub library, identifying sentence boundaries by detecting pauses of 400 ms based on decibel full-scale (dBFS) thresholds. Incoming audio chunks—streamed via REST from a Linphone client—were buffered and continuously analyzed in a dedicated thread for non-silent intervals. We also experimented with a voice activity detection (VAD) approach, which produced inferior results, likely due to its sensitivity to noise and lack of temporal context. In future work, we aim to ex-

plore more advanced segmentation strategies, such as frequency-based features or neural models trained for prosodic boundary detection.

Two STT models were investigated, namely:

- Vosk⁹, an open-source architecture based on the Kaldi speech recognition toolkit.
- Whisper¹⁰, a general-purpose speech recognition model developed by OpenAI [9].

Both models performed well in terms of accuracy and could be implemented in standard performing platforms. In our experiments, we analyse and compare both models.

A STT component was implemented that operates as a transcription service from audio to text. It receives an audio message from Linphone, specifically the Speech/text codec filter (see 3.1), runs a transcription model (i.e., Vosk or Whisper) and returns a text message.

3.3 TTS COMPONENT

To provide a service capable of delivering a high-quality user experience, our system aims to recreate the original speaker’s voice in the transcribed audio message. While the experiments in this paper primarily used a standard voice model, we also conducted experiments with zero-shot models, such as YourTTS [10] and XTTS2 [11] from the Coqui TTS framework [12], as well as StyleTTS2 [13]. These models are capable of on-the-fly speaker adaptation using only a few seconds of reference audio from a speaker, enabling highly personalized voice synthesis. Early experiments with these models show promising results with performance comparable to the standard models.

⁹Available at <https://github.com/alphacep/vosk-api>

¹⁰Available at <https://github.com/openai/whisper>

For the purpose of performance evaluation, we focus on a GenAI-based TTS pipeline that synthesizes realistic speech from text. This pipeline consists of two sequential components:

- FastPitch, a fully-parallel TTS model that converts text into mel-spectrograms, conditioned on predicted pitch contours. This allows for control over prosody and intonation, making the output speech more expressive and semantically aligned with the intended message [14].
- HiFi-GAN, a high-fidelity generative adversarial network (GAN) vocoder that synthesizes raw waveforms from mel-spectrograms. Its multi-scale and multi-period discriminators help capture fine-grained temporal patterns, achieving audio quality close to human speech based on mean opinion score (MOS) evaluations [15].

A TTS component was implemented that receives a text message from the Speech/text codec filter (see Subsection 3.1), runs a GenAI transcription model (using FastPitch and HiFi-GAN) and returns an audio message that is reproduced by Linphone.

3.4 MQTT TRANSPORT COMPONENT

This component handles message publishing and subscription between different users (in our case, Linphone VMs) through the use of topics.

Based on our prior work in [2] the following topic structure is used:

```
FMN-id/country-id/team-id/node-id/service-type
```

The topic structure inherently embeds a hierarchical structure. The first fields are unique identifiers for the federation, country, team and node (i.e., sender or receiver in our case). The service-type is used to refer to specific services, such as location (used to transmit position coordinates) or, in the case of this work, “communications”. Below the “communications” topic, we create the additional identifier “channel-id” referring to a specific recipient or group. Finally, different media types used in communication are foreseen, such as:

- “chat” for text-based communication
- “audio” for audio-based communication (in our case, a text message is redirected to the speech-codec filter component)
- “video for communication using video
- “file” for exchange of files

In this way, the following structure is proposed to support voice and chat communications:

```
FMN-id/country-id/team-id/node-id
/service-type/channel-id/media-type
```

A special communication channel is defined to be used for broadcasting purposes, with id “_broadcasting”.

As an example, an audio converted message sent by node A to node B is published to the following topic:

```
FMN-id/country-id/team-id/A/communications/B/audio
```

It is noted the following:

- The topic structure implicitly applies a hierarchical structure
- Node A should have write permissions to topics below its id.
- Node B should have read permission to communication topics where its id is mentioned.

In case an audio converted message is to be broadcast to a team, the following topic is used:

```
FMN-id/country-id/team-id/_broadcast
/communications/_broadcast/audio
```

Ideally, audio (and video) based communications would function via real-time full-duplex streams however this requires high throughput (order of many kbps or Mbps) and low latency (below the second). Since a tactical network will not support such requirements, our approach is to significantly reduce the data rate by resorting to a message-based middleware and transcription services.

For purposes of auditing and control, the following data structure is defined for each generated message.

- Timestamp [int64]: epoch time (ms) in UTC
- Source [string]: id of the sender node
- Destination [string]: id of the receiving node
- Message [string]: text as converted from audio

3.5 DATA FLOW

In the implemented solution that followed a modular approach, we defined RESTful interfaces following OpenAPI specifications [16] for the STT, TTS and MQTT-Transport components running in each Linphone VM. These components were deployed as Docker containers for convenience. The methods of these interfaces can be seen in the sequence diagram in Figure 2. This separation makes the overall system very modular and flexible, allowing parallel component development between authors and enabling to easily change the used STT and TTS models in the future. As shown in the sequence diagram, both ends (Linphone (1) and Linphone (2)) first initialize their STT, TTS, and MQTT-Transport components. Audio captured by Linphone is forwarded in small chunks (currently 100

Figure 2: Sequence diagram illustrating the implemented process to transmit an audio message. The left and right sides refer to the sender and receiver respectively.

ms) to the STT component. These chunks are buffered in a queue and continuously monitored for sentence boundaries using silence detection, based on a pause threshold of 400 ms. When a complete sentence is detected, the buffered audio is transcribed into text and returned. The resulting text is then passed to the MQTT-Transport component, which encapsulates it into a predefined data structure and transmits it to the corresponding Linphone instance via the MQTT/UDP-based message distribution middleware.

The message is then received by the MQTT-Transport component of Linphone (2) and forwarded to the speech/text codec filter. This filter passes the text to the TTS component, which generates a corresponding audio sample. The resulting audio is then injected into the Linphone processing chain, where it can be either played through the speaker or recorded to a WAV file.

4 EXPERIMENTATION RESULTS

We conducted an experiment to evaluate the feasibility of our approach by deploying two nodes — Node 1 as the sender and Node 2 as the receiver — communicating over a tactical network emulated by the Swiss radio model using EMANE (as described in Section 3 and illustrated in Figure 1). The radios were configured to use the narrowband (VHF) waveform, providing a throughput of 10 kbps.

For STT, we tested two models for comparison: Vosk and Whisper. For text-to-speech (TTS), we employed FastPitch and HiFi-GAN. Message distribution was handled via MQTT/UDP.

The input data consisted of 32 pre-recorded English

audio files in WAV format, evenly split between American and British English, and balanced across male and female speakers. Each file contained three to four spoken sentences, yielding a total of 112 sentences. For reference transcriptions, we used the largest Whisper model (whisper-large), which provides high transcription accuracy. Manual verification of random samples confirmed these to be reliable ground truth. For real-time processing, we used the lighter whisper-english-base model due to its significantly lower computational requirements. All English samples were taken from the American and British English portions of the multilingual ITU-T P.50 Appendix I corpus, which provides standardized speech material across 20 languages.

We first ran the experiment using the MELPe codec instead of the speech-to-text approach. At the restricted 10 kbps data rate, MELPe failed to produce intelligible audio — playback at the receiver resembled slow-motion speech. This was likely due to bandwidth limitations delaying audio frames, introducing gaps in the stream. Since Linphone records continuously into a WAV file, these gaps are preserved, resulting in playback that accurately reflects what would be heard in real time through the speaker.

In contrast, using the speech-to-text pipeline, the corpus samples were transcribed to text, published to the appropriate MQTT topic, received by the subscriber node (Node 2), and converted back into speech with realistic voice modulation.

We analyzed PCAP captures for a representative audio sample containing four spoken sentences (“The ship was torn apart on the sharp reef. Sickness kept

him home the third week. The box will host seven gifts at once. Jazz and swing fans like fast music.”). The total transmitted data, including all headers and SIP signaling, amounted to 25,739 bytes for MELPe, 25,131 bytes for Lyra, and 7,055 bytes for the STT-based approach (which uses SIP for signaling but MQTT/UDP for media transmission). This corresponds to a reduction of approximately $3.6\times$ compared to MELPe and $3.5\times$ compared to Lyra.

When isolating only the media transmission—excluding SIP signaling and other control overhead—the differences become even more pronounced. MELPe used 18,368 bytes, Lyra 17,736 bytes, and the STT-based approach just 1,152 bytes. This results in a reduction of about $16\times$ compared to MELPe and $15\times$ compared to Lyra. These figures include all RTP, UDP, and IP headers (or MQTT/UDP/IP in the case of STT) and reflect the actual payload transmission required by each approach.

Notably, SIP signaling alone accounted for several kilobytes in each configuration. While SIP was used for session establishment across all scenarios, media transport differed: MELPe and Lyra relied on RTP, whereas the STT-based setup used MQTT over UDP. Replacing SIP with a more lightweight signaling protocol could further reduce the total transmission footprint, particularly for short or intermittent interactions.

To further evaluate the effectiveness of the speech-to-text pipeline, we analyzed two key performance metrics:

- **Transcription accuracy** (objective assessment), measured using Word Error Rate (WER), which quantifies the proportion of incorrectly transcribed words per sentence.
- **Message delay** (objective assessment), defined as the time between the end of a spoken sentence and the start of its playback on Linphone 2. This includes the time for sentence detection, STT transcription, MQTT/UDP transmission, and TTS synthesis.

4.1 TRANSCRIPTION ACCURACY RESULTS

Regarding transcription accuracy (cf. Figure 3 and Table 1), both STT models — Vosk (english-medium) and Whisper (english-base) — demonstrated high accuracy in transcribing the audio samples. The observed outliers are primarily due to sentence segmentation errors, where two sentences were inadvertently merged into a single input. While the transcriptions themselves may still be accurate, the mismatch with the ground truth during Word Error Rate (WER) calculation results in artificially high error scores. This issue could be mitigated in future work by implementing a more robust sentence detection strategy.

Figure 3: Boxplot of Word Error Rate (WER) per sentence comparing Vosk and Whisper STT models.

Table 1: Statistical summary of Word Error Rate (WER) per sentence for Vosk and Whisper STT models.

	Vosk	Whisper
min	0.000	0.000
max	1.000	1.000
mean	0.091	0.071
median	0.000	0.000

4.2 MESSAGE DELAY RESULTS

We measured the end-to-end delay from the end of a spoken sentence to the beginning of its playback at the receiver, decomposed into four contributing components — sentence detection, STT processing, MQTT transport, and TTS synthesis — with the total delay representing their sum.

We obtained the results shown in Figure 4 and Tables 2-6.

- **Sentence Detection Delay:** Median values were similar for both models—341 ms for Vosk and 342 ms for Whisper—indicating consistent pause-based segmentation performance.
- **STT Delay:** Whisper was faster, with a median delay of 366 ms compared to Vosk’s 399 ms. Whisper also had a lower mean STT delay (377 ms vs. 464 ms), suggesting it handled inference more efficiently in this setup.
- **MQTT Transport Delay:** As expected under constrained network conditions (a TDMA-based waveform with 10 kbps total, shared between nodes), the MQTT message delivery accounted for a significant portion of the delay: median values were 580 ms for Vosk and 655 ms for Whisper.
- **TTS Delay:** Both models exhibited similar TTS performance. Median values were 321 ms for Vosk and 319 ms for Whisper using FastPitch and HiFi-GAN, showing that the final audio rendering step was consistent and efficient.
- **Total Delay:** The cumulative median delay was

Figure 4: Boxplot showing measured delays (in ms) across system components, including mean, quartiles, outliers, minimum, and maximum values. Delay components: (1) Sentence detection — time from the end of a spoken sentence to its detection; (2) STT — time to transcribe speech to text; (3) MQTT transport — time between message transmission and reception; (4) TTS — time to synthesize speech from text; (5) Total — cumulative end-to-end delay.

1785 ms for Vosk and 1647 ms for Whisper. In both cases, the total delay remained under 2 seconds, which is acceptable for many tactical voice communication scenarios.

Overall, considering that traditional codecs like MELPe failed entirely under these network constraints, our approach demonstrates a clear advantage: by leveraging GenAI, it enables intelligible voice communication even in severely bandwidth-constrained tactical networks.

Table 2: Statistical summary of sentence detection delay (in ms) for the two runs with Vosk and Whisper STT models.

	Vosk	Whisper
min	243.000	253.000
max	1030.000	1080.000
mean	453.857	469.027
median	341.500	342.000

5 DISCUSSION

In this paper, we explored the application of communication services in constrained, low-data-rate tactical networks. Future fully connected soldier systems face critical challenges—most notably, limited data rates

Table 3: Statistical summary of STT delay (in ms) for Vosk and Whisper STT models.

	Vosk	Whisper
min	152.000	90.000
max	2558.000	1288.000
mean	463.920	376.964
median	398.500	366.000

Table 4: Statistical summary of MQTT transport delay (in ms) for the two runs with Vosk and Whisper STT models.

	Vosk	Whisper
min	382.000	384.000
max	1353.000	2455.000
mean	666.232	749.786
median	579.500	654.500

Table 5: Statistical summary of TTS delay (in ms) (FastPitch + HiFi-GAN) for the two runs with Vosk and Whisper STT models.

	Vosk	Whisper
min	140.000	159.000
max	718.000	721.000
mean	334.750	335.072
median	321.000	319.000

Table 6: Statistical summary of total delay (in ms) for the two runs with Vosk and Whisper STT models.

	Vosk	Whisper
min	1188.000	1160.000
max	3711.000	3962.000
mean	1918.759	1927.126
median	1785.000	1647.000

and intermittent connectivity. In remote or contested environments, maintaining reliable communication is difficult yet essential for situational awareness and coordinated command. Audio communication plays a key role in such scenarios, particularly when voice is the only viable modality.

We developed a demonstrator system integrating AI-driven technologies and demonstrated its feasibility under tactical network conditions. Our results show that this approach substantially reduces the data transmission footprint while maintaining real-time usability and a high user experience.

On the transmission side, both Vosk and Whisper STT models reliably produced transcriptions in under one second, with high accuracy. On the receiving side, generative AI-based TTS using FastPitch and HiFi-GAN generated natural-sounding speech with consistent performance. Early tests with zero-shot TTS models (e.g., YourTTS, XTTS2, StyleTTS2) demonstrated their ability to recreate speaker-specific voice characteristics using only a few seconds of reference audio—an important capability for speaker identification and situational awareness.

Compared to conventional MELPe and Lyra codecs, our speech-to-text approach reduced the transmitted media data volume by approximately 93.7% and 93.5%, respectively. When including protocol overhead (e.g., SIP signaling), the total data volume was reduced by approximately 72%. These reductions highlight the efficiency of transmitting compact text instead of continuous audio streams, enabling effective communication even over TDMA-based links with very low data rates.

The use of TTS also enables enhanced communication capabilities beyond simple voice reproduction. Potential extensions include subtitle display for hearing-impaired or noisy conditions, and real-time language translation—features supported by the multilingual capabilities of both Vosk and Whisper. However, limitations remain: sentence boundary detection is not perfect, cloned voice models must be preloaded at the receiver, and current TTS systems still struggle to fully capture speaker-specific prosody and emotional tone.

For message exchange, we used a lightweight MQTT-over-UDP transport layer, favoring performance over guaranteed delivery. This trade-off is acceptable in many tactical scenarios, and custom reliability mech-

anisms can be added if needed. The adopted MQTT topic structure supports easy scalability for multi-node, multinational deployments.

Although the current tests involved only two nodes in a controlled setup, the results demonstrate the system’s viability. Future work will evaluate performance in multi-node environments to assess behavior under more realistic, mission-scale conditions.

Power consumption is also an important consideration. Portable soldier devices must be lightweight and energy-efficient. As AI models are computationally demanding, deploying efficient models and optimizing performance–energy trade-offs are key to operational viability.

Finally, although security risks such as AI-generated spoofing should not be overlooked, they were not a focus of this work. Authentication and verification mechanisms must be integrated in future implementations to prevent potential misuse.

6 CONCLUSION

This paper presented a practical approach for enabling voice communication in constrained tactical networks by combining AI-based STT, efficient message transmission over MQTT/UDP, and high-quality GenAI TTS. The solution significantly reduces the required network data rate—achieving a reduction of approximately 72% in overall transmitted data volume (including signaling overhead like SIP and RTP), and up to 93.7% reduction when focusing only on the media portion—while maintaining operational usability and responsiveness.

Both Vosk and Whisper STT models performed reliably, achieving fast and accurate transcriptions. On the receiving side, the TTS system based on FastPitch and HiFi-GAN produced natural-sounding speech with consistent performance. Importantly, preliminary experiments with zero-shot TTS models (e.g., YourTTS, XTTS2) show strong potential to reproduce speaker-specific voice characteristics using only a few seconds of reference audio—an important step toward preserving speaker identity and improving situational context in voice communication.

The complete end-to-end pipeline maintained a total delay below two seconds, making it suitable for time-sensitive coordination in tactical operations. By transmitting short text messages instead of continuous audio streams, the system enables effective communication over narrowband, intermittent links typical of dismantled or contested environments.

Future work involves further validating system performance in multi-node, operationally representative deployments, specifically by instantiating more nodes and exchanging more messages to test the solution at a larger and more realistic scale. The system’s

modular architecture—built around RESTful APIs and containerized using Docker—offers high flexibility and ease of integration with existing or future battlefield services. This makes it well suited for extension and scaling in NATO federated tactical networks and next-generation soldier systems.

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